

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-2-174-IG-4% 40 rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0722
Vial:	5	Acq. Method Set:	4%210400 40
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 2 174
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	11.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	7/23/2022 9:31:43 AM CST		
Date Processed:	3/9/2023 8:00:07 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.080	625474	13.98	89418
2	5.336	1591672	35.57	205465
3	5.772	1617565	36.15	198508
4	6.205	640305	14.31	74903

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-2-228-IG-4% 40 asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0
Vial:	99	Acq. Method Set:	4%210400 40
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 2 228
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	11.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	7/9/2022 5:28:00 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/9/2023 8:01:42 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.145	100124	0.88	12514
2	5.436	24098	0.21	2777
3	5.793	11138826	97.61	1245451
4	6.172	148976	1.31	15210